

To ensure that international rankings promote positive competition, it is important to ensure that the rankings are based on a comprehensive set of metrics and data and accurately reflect the realities of a country or organization's performance. It is also important to ensure that the rankings do not prioritize short-term gains over long-term sustainability and that they promote social and environmental responsibility. Finally, it is important to promote collaboration and cooperation between countries and organizations to achieve shared goals and drive progress in a sustainable and equitable way.

Overall, research on international rankings and global competition is a critical area of study that can

help us understand how to promote innovation, progress, and sustainability in today's interconnected world. Also consolidating international partnerships is a critical strategy for promoting global cooperation and achieving shared goals in today's interconnected world. By building strong relationships, working together on shared challenges, and promoting mutual understanding, we can create a more peaceful, prosperous, and sustainable world for all.

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SOCIAL PROBLEMS OF THE YOUTH OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

This research focuses on the social problems faced by the youth in Kazakhstan, particularly exploring the manifestations of these problems through the influence of social subcultures and social media. The study aims to understand the nature and extent of social problems affecting Kazakh youth, identify risk factors and protective factors, develop effective prevention and intervention strategies, and assess the relationship between subcultures and the negative impact of social media. The research utilizes a literature review to analyze existing research, conducts a survey among representatives of the Kazakh youth, and investigates the prevalence and patterns of social problems among Kazakh youth through the lens of subcultures. The findings will contribute to a better understanding of the social problems faced by Kazakh youth and inform the development of interventions to address these issues.

Keywords: social problems, subcultures, youth, Kazakhstan, mental health, development.

Introduction

A social problem is a condition or issue that affects a significant number of people in a society, and is considered to be harmful or undesirable by a large segment of the population. Social problems can take many forms, including economic, political, environmental, and cultural issues. It is readily apparent that youth are more likely to be under pressure of social problems because youth are in a development stage where they are still forming their identities and are particularly susceptible to external influences. Therefore, the importance of conducting the study of social problems of the youth is extremely high, especially when it comes to the potential of the younger generation.

The future of society depends on the well-being of youth. Addressing social problems among youth can help ensure that young people have the resources and opportunities they need to reach their full potential and contribute to society in meaningful ways. Moreover, many social problems can have long-lasting effects on young people, affecting their physical and mental health, educational attainment, employment opportunities, and overall well-being. It is especially important for a young country like Kazakhstan to pay attention to the social problems of the youth, because the youth

generation is the key to further strengthening of the stability of Kazakhstan. In this research, the main goal is to provide the information about the social problems of the younger generation of Kazakhstan, highlighting manifestation of the problems in various forms, including influence of social media and representatives of specific subcultures like “punk” subculture, gang members, etc.

Formulation of the research problem

The social problems of the youth in Kazakhstan is an important dilemma which requires investigating these problems more deeply. Subgroups and specific subcultures actually represent how youth are suffering from the social problems, including poverty, inequality, gender-based violence, drug and alcohol abuse, child abuse, and domestic violence. In this research, understanding the social problems proper to the youth, we would like to determine the way social subcultures are organized, the causes of their creation, the reason why younger generations support and participate in these subgroups, and the way social media may affect this.

Aims and objectives

Aims:

-Understand the nature and extent of social problems affecting youth in Kazakhstan

-Identify the factors that increase young people's risk of experiencing social problems, as well as the protective factors that can help mitigate those risk

-Develop effective prevention and intervention strategies that can be implemented to address social problems affecting Kazakh youth.

Objectives:

-To analyze a literature review of the existing research covering this issue.

-To determine the prevalence and patterns of social problems among Kazakh youth, such as substance abuse, unemployment, mental health issues, and gender-based violence through the essence of the subgroups, i.e. how members of cultural subgroups experience different social problems.

-To illustrate the relationship between the subgroups and negative impact of social media

-To find the protective factors that can help mitigate the risks of social problems among Kazakh youth, such as positive peer relationships, supportive families, and access to education and health care

-To identify the barriers and facilitators to addressing social problems among Kazakh youth, such as limited resources, or cultural norms.

-To conduct a survey among the representatives of the Kazakh youth.

Literature review

In our research we used 5 sources of information, where the problems of subcultures were raised, especially psychological aspect. Analyzing several works we found out the main things to focus on, including manifestation of social problems (alcohol and drug abuse, cruelty, violence, attitude to social values).

M. Kovalchuk, I. Tarkhanova in their research illustrated negative trends among the youth in Russia, including their wish to get as much pleasure from life as possible, however it may finish with addiction to drugs and alcohol. In many cases, the youth also believe that alcohol and drug consumption may be something even helpful for them to experience more emotions. They believe they can be free of all problems they have, experience a sense of belonging to a group of people. [1]

Another thing to pay attention to is the violence among the youth. In many cases people do not show aggression being alone, it is mainly demonstrated among groups of people, and the research of Rogotnev I. illustrates how subcultures in Russia behave in society. Their ideology is based on some principles that determine their status and identity in society. [2]

In research of Mosienko L. the problem of social values among the youth is raised. On the one hand, there may be positive ways how the younger generation develops in terms of morality, intelligence, society, family, aesthetics. However, there might be some deviations from the norms generated by society, which may be considered both positive and negative, for instance, relationship with elders is illustrated, what is definitely develops in negative direction. [3]

Another source of information, written by Akhmetov A., shows the cultural diversity of Astana, Kazakhstan, including distribution of social subcultures like "Emo", "Goth", "hip-hop", etc. among people aged from 14 to 28 years. [4]

The last but not least is the research conducted in the UK, which describes long term analysis conducted by Lucy Bowes, Rebecca Carnegie, Rebecca Pearson, Becky Mars, Lucy Biddle, Barbara Maughan, Glyn Lewis, Charles Fernyhough, Jon Heron, where the problems of subcultures, mainly of "Emo" were illustrated. [5]

Social problems of youth and its forms

A social problem is a condition or situation that is perceived to be harmful or undesirable by a significant number of people in a society. Social problems can take many different forms, but they generally involve issues that affect the well-being and quality of life of individuals and communities. Examples of social problems include poverty, unemployment, homelessness, drug addiction, discrimination, violence, and environmental degradation. These issues are often complex and multifaceted, and may be influenced by a variety of social, economic, cultural, and political factors. Social problems are not necessarily universal across all societies, and may vary in terms of their severity and prevalence depending on the specific context. However, they are generally recognized as having a significant impact on the functioning and stability of societies, and often require collective action and intervention to address. Young people are particularly vulnerable to social problems because they are still in the process of developing their identities and establishing their place in the world. Many young people may feel overwhelmed by the challenges they face, and may not have the resources or support they need to navigate them successfully. Young people can experience social problems in a variety of ways, depending on their individual circumstances and the specific issue at hand. Here are some examples:

1. Unemployment: The high level of youth unemployment is one of the significant social problems in Kazakhstan. Despite a growing economy, young people often struggle to find employment, leading to low income, frustration, and a sense of hopelessness.

2. Substance abuse: Drug and alcohol abuse is another significant problem faced by young people in Kazakhstan. Many young people turn to substance abuse as a way of coping with the stress and challenges they face. [1]

3. Mental health: Mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and stress are on the rise among young people in Kazakhstan. The lack of resources and support for mental health services further exacerbates the problem.

4. Education: Access to quality education remains a challenge for many young people in Kazakhstan. The quality of education in rural areas is particularly low, leading to disparities in opportunities between urban and rural youth.

5. Social inequality: Social inequality is a significant problem in Kazakhstan, with young people from disadvantaged backgrounds facing greater challenges in accessing education, employment, and other opportunities. [2]

In this context, the research focuses on what may be the causes of these social problems. We decided to concentrate on different types of manifestations of

these problems, and in our opinion those are social subgroups, like “emo”, “goth”, “metal”, “hip-hop”, “anime fans”, etc. [4] In real life we may observe how those social subgroups are following the same interests, however many of them may be associated with various ways of non-standard behavior, including aggression, violence, mental instability, alcohol and drug abuse. On the one hand, the main idea of how social subcultures are formed is that they experience social stigma and discrimination, lack of social support, chronic stress. But, on the other hand, there is some relation with the manifestation of those problems which is observed in behavior of representatives of those subgroups. Some of them may represent friendly ideas, while others, especially in developing and poor countries may be directly related to various forms of aggression, including gender and race inequality, aggressive nationalism, extremist movements. [3]

Analysis of data gathered from studies about teenagers in the UK

In order to try to reproduce the research method, we decided to investigate the way the similar studies were conducted. Therefore, we decided to take into account “Risk of depression and self-harm in teenagers

identifying with goth subculture: a longitudinal cohort study” research conducted by Lucy Bowes, Rebecca Carnegie, Rebecca Pearson, Becky Mars, Lucy Biddle, Barbara Maughan, Glyn Lewis, Charles Fernyhough, Jon Heron. The main goal of their research was to illustrate the comparison between youth self-identified as goths and not self-identified, whether each group experienced more clinical depression and self-harm in comparison with another one. In this longitudinal research 14 541 pregnant women initially enrolled and returned at least one questionnaire or attended a Children in Focus clinic. The researchers assessed depressive mood and self-harm at 15 years with the Development and Wellbeing Assessment (DAWBA) questionnaire, and depression and self-harm at 18 years using the Clinical Interview Schedule-Revised. The researchers calculated the prospective association between goth identification at 15 years and depression and self-harm at 18 years using logistic regression analyses, controlling for potentially confounding variables such as gender, socio-economic status, and prior mental health problems. Eight different social groups were identified during the research: “sporty”, “populars”, “skaters”, “chavs”, “loners”, “keeners”, “bimbos”, and “goths”.

	Low goth self-identification (n=4709)	High goth self-identification (n=648)	p value
Gender			
Female	2453 (52%)	374 (58%)	0.01
Male	2256 (48%)	274 (42%)	0.01
Parental social class			
High (professional, managerial, or skilled occupations)	2072 (44%)	286 (44%)	0.94
Low (partly skilled or unskilled occupations)	2637 (56%)	362 (56%)	0.95
Mother with degree	871 (18%)	119 (18%)	0.94
Maternal depression score during pregnancy	6.5 (4.8)	7.0 (5.1)	0.02
Maternal history of severe depression	283 (6%)	64 (10%)	<0.001
Bullying			
Bullied at age of 8 years	1822 (39%)	307 (47%)	<0.001
Bullied at age of 13 years	542 (12%)	106 (16%)	0.02
Life events score at age 3-5 years	2.7 (2.5)	3.1 (2.8)	<0.001
Strengths and difficulties (age 12 years)			
Prosocial score	8.4 (1.6)	8.3 (1.7)	0.13
Hyperactivity score	2.6 (2.1)	2.8 (2.2)	0.04
Emotional symptoms score	1.4 (1.7)	1.6 (1.7)	0.03
Conduct problems score	1.1 (1.3)	1.1 (1.3)	0.24
Peer problems score	1.0 (1.4)	1.3 (1.6)	<0.001
Total difficulties score	5.8 (4.4)	6.5 (4.7)	<0.001
MFQ score >11			
MFQ>11 at age of 10 years	198 (4%)	27 (4%)	0.97
MFQ>11 at age 12-5 years	231 (5%)	51 (8%)	<0.001
MFQ>11 at 13-5 years	364 (8%)	115 (18%)	<0.001
DAWBA depression score at age of 15 years	3.2 (4.5)	5.7 (6.7)	<0.001
Self-harm at age of 15 years	457 (10%)	166 (26%)	<0.001
Self-perception at age of 11 years			
Kind	3899 (83%)	509 (79%)	<0.001
Friendly	4309 (92%)	584 (90%)	0.02
Confident	2731 (58%)	360 (56%)	<0.001
Sporty	2816 (60%)	262 (40%)	<0.001
Good looking	1681 (36%)	190 (29%)	<0.001
Easily bored	1333 (28%)	226 (35%)	0.01
Different from others	739 (16%)	222 (34%)	<0.001
Worries a lot	782 (17%)	154 (24%)	<0.001
Messes about a lot	1267 (27%)	211 (33%)	0.02
Temperament at age of 6 years (child in top quartile)			
Emotionality	749 (16%)	157 (24%)	<0.001
Activity	739 (16%)	80 (12%)	0.20
Shyness	871 (18%)	120 (19%)	0.94
Sociability	876 (19%)	123 (19%)	0.17

Data are n (%) or mean (SD). Self-identification by binary variable of low self-identification (not at all to somewhat) or high self-identification (more than somewhat to very much).

Table 1: Baseline characteristics of study participants according to goth self-identification

In Table 1, broad information about distribution of participants is provided. We may observe that 5357 teenagers self-identified as goths are included in these studies, including 4709 respondents with low self-identification and 648 respondents with high self-identification.

And there were multiple criteria to classify participants. This approach is eventually used in regression analysis. Also, it is important to note that only approximate results are provided, and p-value score is used in order to represent the confidence of some hypothesis or classification.

	Number of participants (n=5357)	Number of participants with data for goth self-identification at 15 years and outcomes at 18 years (n=3694)	Depression		Self-harm	
			OR (95% CI)	p value	OR (95% CI)	p value
Linear effect*	5357	3694	1.36 (1.23-1.49)	p<0.001	1.52 (1.42-1.63)	p<0.001
Not at all	2759	1841	Reference	-	Reference	-
Not very much	1234	884	1.16 (0.83-1.62)	-	1.52 (1.20-1.93)	-
Somewhat	716	523	1.63 (1.14-2.34)	-	2.33 (1.80-3.02)	-
More than somewhat	410	292	2.33 (1.56-3.47)	-	3.65 (2.72-4.89)	-
Very much	238	154	3.67 (2.33-4.79)	-	5.14 (3.58-7.36)	-
LR test	5357	3694	χ^2 38.99	p<0.001	χ^2 132.65	p<0.001

OR=odds ratio, LR=likelihood ratio. *Goth identification was treated as a continuous variable; therefore, the linear effect refers to OR of depression for a one point increase in goth identification. The LR test provides a test for the dose-response trend.

Table 2: Odds ratio for depression and self-harm at 18 years for each category of goth identification

	Depression		Self-harm	
	OR (95% CI)	p value	OR (95% CI)	p value
Unadjusted (n=3694)	1.36 (1.23-1.49)	p<0.001	1.52 (1.42-1.63)	p<0.001
Complete cases (n=2351)	1.39 (1.22-1.58)	p<0.001	1.51 (1.37-1.66)	p<0.001
Adjusted for baseline depression score (n=2351)	1.33 (1.16-1.52)	p<0.001	1.46 (1.32-1.61)	p<0.001
Adjusted for ever self-harmed by 15 years (n=2351)	1.30 (1.14-1.49)	p<0.001	1.33 (1.19-1.48)	p<0.001
Additionally adjusted for all covariates* (n=2351)	1.28 (1.11-1.47)	p<0.001	1.33 (1.19-1.48)	p<0.001
Imputed confounders (n=3694)	1.20 (1.08-1.33)	p<0.001 FMI 0.155	1.28 (1.18-1.39)	p<0.001 FMI 0.155
Imputed outcome (n=342)	1.18 (1.06-1.31)	p=0.002 FMI 0.472	1.25 (1.16-1.36)	p<0.001 FMI 0.469

OR=odds ratio, FMI= fraction of missing information, SMFQ=Short Mood and Feelings Questionnaire. *Gender, previous depression (an SMFQ score of >11 at ages 10, 13, or 16 years), internalising and externalising difficulties at 11 years, self-perception, victimisation by bullies, antenatal depression, maternal history of depression, maternal education, and temperament (emotionality and activity). †The FMI can be used to judge whether the number of imputations is sufficient for analysis. ‡A rule of thumb is that the number of imputations (M) should be more than or equal to 100 × FMI. In our case, the number of imputations (M=100) was sufficient.

Table 3: Odds ratio for depression and self-harm given for each category increase in goth identification

According to Table 2, young people who identified as goths were more likely to experience depression and self-harm compared to those who did not identify as goths. Specifically, those who somewhat identified as goths were 1.6 times more likely to have scores in the clinical range for depression at 18 years, while those who very much identified as goths were more than three times as likely. For each unit increase in goth affiliation, the odds of depression increased by 1.36.

Similarly, those who somewhat identified as goths were 2.33 times more likely to report having self-harmed, while those who very much identified as goths were more than five times as likely. For each unit increase in affiliation with the goth subculture, the odds of self-harm increased by 1.52.

Of all subcultures identified, those who identified as goths very much were most at risk of depression and self-harm, with 18% having scores in the clinical range for depression and 37% reporting self-harm at 18 years of age. Comparatively, those who identified as sporty were least likely to have depression and to have self-harmed at age 18 years, with only 4% having depression and 6% reporting self-harm.

Eventually, we need to understand that studies were conducted in UK, therefore some assumptions may be not applicable in Kazakhstan, but our main goal was to understand the way scientists in UK conducted a research, i.e. how they formulated the problem, found out goals of their studies, made calculations and statistical analysis to get results. This study clearly illus-

trated the two different ways how teenagers self-identified as goths experience more mental issues, compared with those that are not self-identified as goths. [5]

Analysis of results gathered after the survey conducted in Kazakhstan

Background: Researches that were conducted in Kazakhstan actually didn't have enough statistical analysis concerning mental issues of youth. Our main focus is to provide a survey, which will show all influencing factors that describe the state of this problem. We also conduct comparative analysis with the survey conducted in UK

Methods: We conducted a survey, which consists of 18 questions. Each question takes into account the most important qualitative and quantitative factors which are needed to analyze mental issues of representatives and non-representatives of subcultures. In general, people from 15 to 24 years, but there also was a small percent of respondents who were either younger or older than the main group

Findings: Of 46 respondents, 37 of them either considered themselves not being a part of any subculture or just had lower self-identification as a participant of such subcultures. On the other hand, we had 9 respondents who highly self-identified themselves as a part of subcultures, including goths, bikers, emo, etc. According to our analysis, we concluded that there are many parameters that are actually almost similar both for non-representatives and representatives (i.e. mental issues, conditions which include apathy, sadness, low self-esteem)

Table 4

Statistics about non-representatives of any subcultures

Table 5

Statistics about representatives of subcultures

According to our investigations, we need to pay more attention to those factors:

1) There are 37 non-representatives who feel low self-identification as participants of subcultures and 9 representatives of subcultures who feel high self-identification as participants of subcultures. (Next, let's call them group 1 and group 2 respectively)

2) Both group1 and group2 have almost the same attitude towards bad habits like alcohol and cigarettes.

3) Only 28% of all respondents believe that activities of subcultures are strongly related to alcohol and drug abuse.

4) On average, group2 feels more shy when they want to share their interests and opinions with family and friends (4.22 out of 5 for group2, 3.76 out of 5 for group1)

5) 44% of respondents of group2 (against 24% of group1) actually were the subject of criticism when it comes to their life perception, hobbies, and interests

6) Almost half of all respondents believe that songs about alcohol and drug abuse may be the key factor of alcohol abuse among youth in Kazakhstan.

7) When it comes to sadness, loneliness, apathy, low self-esteem, both group1 and group2 have relatively similar results.

Comparative analysis of studies in UK and Kazakhstan

Based on both studies, we need to mention that, of course, the scale of research in the UK is much broader than this one in Kazakhstan, because we were able to gather information about 46 respondents, which is a relatively small sample, whereas the research in the UK conducted analysis among over 5000 respondents. "Risk of depression and self-harm in teenagers identifying with goth subculture: a longitudinal cohort study" is the research which started in 1991 and was finished in 2015. Study in the UK actually concludes that youth self-identified as representatives of subcultures are more likely to experience mental issues like alcohol and drug abuse. Also, they might have more bad thoughts about suicide, self-harm, etc. Their research had 8 subgroups, but they mainly focused on goths, whereas in our research we had more subcultures (goths, bikers, emo, punks, rock). Also, it is mentioned that mental issues of parents may also be a huge factor of mental illnesses of subcultures representatives. In our research, we confirmed some results that were discussed in the research conducted in the UK. For instance, factors like alcohol abuse, songs related to drug abuse, and bad habits have positive correlation with the growth of the number of subcultures participants. However, in our opinion, although participants of subcultures experience more mental issues than non-representatives, we believe that participation in subcultures has less correlation with mental issues development among youth, that is, although youth may feel lonely, depressed, have low self-esteem, it doesn't mean that the root cause is the participation in such subcultures. We strongly believe that it is only partially related, because there are several examples of cruel and extremist behavior of those representatives, but it DOESN'T mean that all representatives actually have the same lifestyle and behavior. Many people in our research mentioned that people feeling sad, lonely, exhausted actually may need to find more ways to communicate with people, find new friends or people who have the same interests, that is the main reason why subcultural flows are created.

Conclusion

Analyzing the problems of youth, we raised the topic of the problems of people who are members of

subcultures. People who belong to subcultures, although they have a hobby, suffer from psychological health diseases and bad habits. However, there is a false opinion that subcultures are the cause of human problems. Entering a subculture, a person may already be psychologically vulnerable. This statement was supported by the results of the study, in which it turned out that people with and without subcultural interests equally often have bad habits. The importance of this research is in raising the topic of youth problems, researching its causes and collecting relevant statistics. The results of our research can also be used to study the consequences of youth problems, or to study the root of the problem in more detail.

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